

MORIAH: MORINGA AND RICE BLOTTING PAPER

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MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper

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Abstract

Due to the innumerable benefits and uses of moringa and rice in terms of health and food products, many researches were conducted mainly for the exploration of these components. However, despite their much-studied properties in various applications, skincare was one area that they have missed. Researchers lacked investigations about how moringa and rice can be used externally, much more to be used together in one product. Because of this, the researchers intended to discover the potential of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper and to explore such areas to find factual evidence as to why these components are beneficial for human skin. Specifically, they aimed to answer several questions regarding the acceptability of the product in terms of smell, texture, and thickness, as well as its efficacy in terms of strength and oil absorption. Moreover, they also identified the significant differences between the experimented and the controlled products. The results showed that Moringa and rice are acceptable components in making a blotting paper, however the product was not suitable for other paper uses as it did not meet the strength classification requirements. Although, the product was effective in terms of oil absorption and the facial oil content of each respondent was found to be better absorbed using MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper compared to a commercially produced product.

Keywords: *moringa oleifera, rice, skin, blotting paper*

Introduction

People nowadays are becoming more mindful when it comes to having healthy skin; and to achieve a healthy and glowing skin, skincare is a must. As stated by Joshi (2022), taking care of your skin on your face and body is an important routine that you should adopt. Having a good skincare regimen will allow you to have healthy and radiant appearance. Not just that, maintaining a healthy ideal skin is the most important because it serves as your body's primary protection. This will help prevent internal organ damage, bone and muscle deterioration, and illness (Branch, 2020).

Moringa oleifera is a tree with many nutritional benefits. According to Cadman (2023), "it has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties" and contains many essential compounds such as vitamin A, vitamin B1 (thiamine), vitamin B2 (riboflavin), vitamin B3 (niacin), vitamin C (ascorbic acid), calcium, potassium, iron, magnesium, and phosphorus. Many people traditionally use moringa as food and for medicinal purposes around the world, and has benefits such as protecting and nourishing skin and hair, treating edema, protecting the liver, preventing and treating cancer, improving eye health, and many more (Cadman, 2023). In addition, according to Jimenez et al. (2017) in "Bioactive Components in Moringa oleifera Leaves Protect against Chronic Disease," Moringa oleifera leaves have been extensively studied, and they have been shown to be beneficial in a variety of chronic conditions, including hypercholesterolemia, high blood pressure, diabetes, insulin resistance, non-alcoholic liver disease, cancer, and overall inflammation.

Rice paste, on the other hand, also has various uses, especially in terms of adding it to food products as a component. According to Haque et al. (2022), the stickiness of rice has the ability to retain shape when made as food products like rice pudding, steamed products, and other dishes. In addition, given the viscous characteristic of rice, people also find it helpful when used as glue, with the ingredients being easy to find at home.

With many researches made exploring the helpful purposes of moringa and rice paste, one of the areas that has not been much focused on is their application to skincare and paper-making. Many researchers emphasize their studies merely on consumable products and their remedial abilities.

However, moringa and rice paste are components that can also be used externally.

According to Section 5 of the House Bill No. 2556 of the House of Representatives, Eighteenth Congress, entitled, "An Act Establishing a National Program for the Malunggay Industry, Appropriating Funds Therefor and for Other Purposes,"

"The Committee shall formulate necessary measures, programs and projects for the advancement and industry-wide development of malunggay."

The section follows a statement that declares that the Committee will intensify research and study on the propagation of moringa to maximize and validate its nutritional and therapeutic benefits and to expand its other potential uses, in conjunction with government research and development organizations, relevant SUCs, and the private sector.

Given the statement, the main goal of this study is to discover other potential uses of moringa and rice paste mixture, especially in terms of skincare. With that being said, the researchers intended to make an oil-blotting paper for skin, with moringa leaves and rice paste as the main components.

In the making of the product, the researchers used moringa leaves as the main element, rice paste to keep the product intact, and tissue paper as a filler. They formulated different ratios of the ingredients to determine the most suitable one to use as a blotting paper. According to Fazon et al. (2014), “Malunggay has many fibers that can be used as handmade paper.” However, despite being strong, the output is expected to be rough, which, in terms of application on the skin, will not be very acceptable. Moreover, according to Kurasaawa and Shoji (1994), in terms of cohesiveness, cooked non-glutinous rice showed middle to low values, based on its superiority and inferiority. Therefore, the ability of rice to unify the components depends on its quality as well.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the acceptability and efficacy of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper. The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of acceptability of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in terms of:
 - 1.1. smell;
 - 1.2. texture; and
 - 1.3. thickness?
2. What is the level of efficacy of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in terms of:
 - 2.1. strength; and
 - 2.2. oil absorption?
3. Is there any significant difference between MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper and commercially available products in terms of oil absorption?

Literature Review

As highlighted by San Juan (2024) upon consultation, the product in question possesses a distinct herbal and woody scent, thanks to the incorporation of moringa. This fragrance, while not overpowering or off-putting, has the potential to appeal to a wide range of consumers due to its unique combination of earthy notes. Additionally, the subtle hint of rice adds a delicate complexity to the overall aroma, further enhancing its allure for those seeking a refreshing and natural olfactory experience.

Texture

The idea behind developing blotting paper is that it should have a comfortable texture when applied to the surface of the skin. The blotting paper is designed to be non-sticky, ensuring that it can be easily applied without any uncomfortable sensations or residue (San Juan, 2024). Additionally, the blotting paper should be smooth to the touch, not have a grainy texture, and generally soft, which further improves its comfort factor when used (San Juan, 2024).

Thickness

Blotting papers are ideally lightweight, pliable, and porous (San Juan, 2024), all of which directly affect the thickness of the product and contribute to its acceptability. With that being said, it should be light and thin, able to reach different areas of the face to absorb oil, and be permeable for facial oils to pass through. Moreover, it should be consistently thin throughout its surface (San Juan, 2024), as it can also affect its appeal and oil-absorbent capacity.

Strength

Jani et al. (2015) study investigates the mechanical properties of rice straw pulp and paper, revealing improved density, freeness, tensile, tear, burst, and folding properties compared to unbeaten paper. Moreover, rice as an alternative material for paper production also made a remarkable performance when it was found out that it has the qualities of paper tear index and paper burst strength making it compatible with Moringa oleifera in making a blotting paper, Kim et al. (2022). Furthermore, in the study “Utilization of Malunggay Stem Fibers (Moringa oleifera) as a component in Paper Making” by Fazon et al. (2014), based on the mixture of malunggay fibers, torn papers, and a cup of glue, the finished product came out as rough, hard, and brittle. Therefore, in this context, Moringa oleifera does not have the durability to withstand external pressures. Additionally, rice straw stands out for its impressive tensile strength, making it an excellent material for producing high-quality paper, Acosta et al. (2021).

Oil absorption

The study found that adding Moringa oleifera extract to creams significantly reduced undesirable skin sebum during winter, suggesting that Moringa oleifera may be an effective intervention for controlling excessive skin sebum secretion, (Ali et al. 2013). Also, Rice flour has skin-lightening effects, promotes skin and hair regrowth, and helps control shine and minimize pores by absorbing excess oil on the skin and hair, (Bellefonds 2020). Moreover, Rice, using the Taguchi experimental model, demonstrated potential for oil absorption with a maximum capacity of 154.43%, (Kakar et al. 2022). Additionally, Rice hulls can be transformed into pulp, which is then used to create various types of paper, including printing, writing, and packaging materials, (Arcena 2017).

Methodology

Research Design

As stated in *Types of Quantitative Research Methods and Designs* (2023), the experimental quantitative research design employs a scientific method, creating processes that enable researchers to test hypotheses and systematically and scientifically investigate causal connections among variables. Considering this, the experimental was the most suitable design for conducting the researcher's study as it corresponded to the study's objective wherein the efficacy of moringa and rice were tested as blotting paper. Sirisilla (2023) added that experimental research design is a structured set of protocols designed for conducting scientific experiments with two sets of variables. Quantitative research stands out as a prime example of experimental research methods. Therefore, an experimental type of research design was fitted to be used in the study for it sought to allow the researchers to assess the efficacy of MORIAH blotting paper for persons with oily skin.

Participants

Seven (7) individuals were selected to be the participants of this study. This included one (1) expert who was consulted to guide the conduct of the experiment. Such professional was selected using purposive sampling, relying on the researchers' knowledge regarding the credibility of the expert in providing insights about the study. Moreover, three (3) grade 11 and three (3) grade 12 students were also included as the respondents who would try the product and answer the questionnaire checklist. Their responses were used for data gathering later on. In addition, the respondents were asked to go through a skin analysis to further determine the effectiveness of its oil absorption.

Instruments

In the development of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper, the researchers ensured that the data and information from the sources were aligned with the purpose of the study.

The main source of data collection was the questionnaire-checklist that had been validated by the experts to ensure that the study addressed the following variables: smell, texture, thickness, strength, and oil absorption. Each variable used a 4-point Likert scale.

<i>Rating Scale</i>	<i>Scale Interval</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
4	3.26 - 4.00	Very Acceptable
3	2.51 - 3.25	Acceptable
2	1.76 - 2.50	Less Acceptable
1	1.00 - 1.75	Not Acceptable

Procedure

The data – specifically the screening – was gathered using a digital questionnaire checklist while the data for the products' acceptability were originally made by the researchers. They formulated questions that were appropriate for addressing the specific objectives of the study. After the questions have been made, the material was provided to the respondents and was answered based on their evaluation of the product. Moreover, the conclusions and recommendations from the respondents were also taken into consideration to address possible improvements to further develop the product.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers refrained from soliciting any sensitive personal information from the participants unless it was deemed absolutely necessary for the study's objectives, thereby ensuring the protection of participants' privacy and upholding ethical standards in research practices.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Acceptability of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in Terms of Smell, Texture, and Thickness

Table 1 showed the level of acceptability of the developed product in terms of smell, texture, and thickness. The product was evaluated by the respondents regarding its smell, texture, and thickness. Each participant gave their own ratings based on a 4-point Likert scale. The smell had an average of 3.17, verbally interpreted as acceptable; its texture had an average of 3.54, interpreted as very acceptable; and its thickness obtained an average of 3.63, verbally interpreted as very acceptable. This means that the product was generally acceptable in terms of its smell, texture, and thickness. This implied that moringa and rice were acceptable components in making a blotting paper.

The result was supported by the study of Malik and Chaudhary (2021) and Li, et al. (2023) wherein aroma is a preferred rice characteristic by consumers and using moringa as component significantly increased its acceptability. Moreover, on the study of Sebua (2019) and Barayuga (2021) the researchers note that paper made out of malunggay bark's texture is deemed acceptable on the market while the texture of the rice hulls as paper scored higher than the commercially done product. In additional, according to Mangundayao

et al. (2019) and Barayuga (2021) moringa leaf extract is an effective sizing agent for paper and the rice fibers are already used in making thin sheets of paper.

Table 1. *The Level of Acceptability of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in Terms of Smell, Texture, and Thickness*

Smell	Mean	Interpretation
1. The product has apparent herbal scent.	3.17	Acceptable
2. The product has apparent rice scent.	2.17	Less Acceptable
3. The product scent is appealing.	3.33	Very Acceptable
4. The product's apparent scent is not noxious.	4.00	Very Acceptable
	3.17	Acceptable
Texture	Mean	Interpretation
1. The product is generally smooth to touch.	3.00	Acceptable
2. The product does not stick to the skin when used.	4.00	Very Acceptable
3. The product does not have a grainy feel.	3.50	Very Acceptable
4. The product feels generally smooth on the skin.	3.67	Very Acceptable
	3.54	Very Acceptable
Thickness	Mean	Interpretation
1. The product is lightweight.	4.00	Very Acceptable
2. The product is pliable.	3.67	Very Acceptable
3. The product is porous.	3.00	Acceptable
4. The product is consistently thin throughout its surface.	3.83	Very Acceptable
	3.63	Very Acceptable

The Level of Efficacy of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in Terms of Strength and Oil Absorption

Table 2 showed the level of efficacy of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in terms of strength. As indicated in the table, the acquired mean of three samples was 0.001475 MPa, verbally interpreted as not acceptable based on the standard tensile strength of a paper in accordance with the SGS-IPS Testing, which ranges from 50 KPa (0.05 MPa) to 1200 KPa (1.2 MPa). This means that the product was not efficient in terms of its tensile strength. From this, it can be implied that the developed product did not pass the criteria of classifying the strength of a paper, hence not suitable for other uses of a paper. Further studies may be conducted to identify the strength of the product, specifically for blotting papers.

The result was supported by the study of Arabi, et al. (2023), entitled, “Banana Stem Fibers as a Component in Making Memo Pad Paper,” which concluded that the alternative memo pad paper had low tensile strength, similar to the outcome of this research’s findings.

Table 2. *Computed Mean on the Level of Efficacy of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in Terms of Strength*

Sample	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Verbal Interpretation
1	0.0013625	Not acceptable
2	0.0016625	Not acceptable
3	0.0014	Not acceptable
Mean	0.001475	Not acceptable

This means that result of before and after usage was statistically significant. It can be implied that the developed product was efficient in terms of oil absorption. According to Ali et al. (2013), Moringa oleifera may be an effective intervention for controlling excessive skin sebum secretion, which supported the result of the study.

Table 3. *The Level of Efficacy of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper in Terms of Oil Absorption*

MORIAH	Mean	Mean diff	Sd	t	df	Sig	Ho	VI
Before	2.75	1.69	1.02	3.63	5	0.01	R	S
After	1.06		0.37					

The Level of Significant Difference of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper and Commercially Available Products in Terms of Oil Absorption

Table 4 reflected the significant differences between MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper and commercially available products

in terms of oil absorption. It could be gleaned from the table that MORIAH had an acquired mean of 1.06 and a standard deviation of 0.37, whereas commercially done blotting paper had an acquired mean of 1.97 and a standard deviation of 0.53, which displayed significant differences in the results with t-values of 3.13047 and p-values of 0.01068 for both variants. This means that there was a significant difference in absorption performance between the Moriah and commercially done blotting papers. The results regarding the facial oil content of each respondent after using Moriah blotting paper demonstrated better oil absorption compared to the commercially done blotting paper, as evidenced by the above- mentioned means and standard deviations.

Table 4. *The Level of Significant Different of MORIAH: Moringa and Rice Blotting Paper and Commercially Available Products in Terms of Oil Absorption*

Group	Mean	Mean diff	Sd	t	df	Sig	Ho	VI
MORIAH	1.06		0.37					
Commercial	1.97	0.91	0.53	3.13	10	0.01	R	S

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings, the researchers concluded the following: Moringa and rice are acceptable components for making blotting paper. Although the product did not meet the strength classification requirements for other paper uses, it was efficient in oil absorption. The MORIAH blotting paper absorbed facial oil better than a commercially produced product.

In light of these conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested: Conduct a parallel study using other locally available herbs and different brands of rice to determine if the smell of rice becomes more evident. Explore other alternatives for filler materials and utilize appropriate tools to measure the product's tensile strength. Consider using other known commercial products for comparison.

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